

PMR Spectral Study of *N*-Nitroso- and *N*-Acetyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines

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In continuation of our work on the chemistry of nitrones, we aimed to synthesise α -aryl-*N*-pyrazolinylnitrones. We started preparing several *N*-nitroso-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines (1) from the parent pyrazolines (2). Eventhough there are several reports on the pmr study of pyrazolines and their derivatives, some of them lack details¹. It is also thought that a comparison of the pmr spectra of the nitroso derivatives with the corresponding acetyl derivatives (3) may lead to some interesting observations. Hence this study was undertaken.

3,5-Diaryl-2-pyrazolines (2) and the acetyl derivatives were prepared by the usual method^{1b}. The nitroso derivatives (1) were prepared from the parent pyrazolines (2) by adding a solution of the latter (0.01 mol) in THF (40 ml) with sodium nitrite (0.7 g) in water (5 ml) at 0°, followed by the addition of dilute HCl (10 ml) dropwise with stirring. The yield, m.p. and ir data of both acetyl and nitroso derivatives are given in Table 1, and the pmr details in Table 2. All the nitroso derivatives (1a-h) show their $\nu_{\text{N=O}}$ stretching at 1580 cm^{-1} which is characteristic for aliphatic monomeric N=O group, ruling out the possibility of any dimeric form.

1; X = NO, 2; X = H, 3; X = COCH₃

a; R₁ = R₂ = Ph, b; R₁ = R₂ = 4-Me.Ph, c; R₁ = R₂ = 4-Cl.Ph, d. R₁ = R₂ = 4-MeO.Ph, e; R₁ = Ph; R₂ = 4-Me.Ph, f; R₁ = Ph; R₂ = 4-MeO.Ph, g; R₁ = 4-MeO.Ph; R₂ = Ph, h; R₁ = 4-Me.Ph; R₂ = Ph.

From Table 2, it can be seen that all the nitroso and acetyl derivatives (1 and 3) show well-defined signals. H_A is the benzylic hydrogen and appears around δ 5.5–5.7 in the acetyl system and around δ 5.8 to 5.9 in the nitroso derivative. This appears as a doublet of doublet with *J* values 12 and 5 Hz. H_B is the hydrogen *cis* and *vicinal* to H_A appearing as a doublet of doublet (*J* 18 and 12 Hz). This hydrogen appears around δ 3.65–3.75 for the acetyl system and around δ 3.85–3.95 for nitroso compounds. The H_C which appears around δ 3.05–3.15 for acetyl compound and around δ 3.2–3.25 for nitroso derivatives is the hydrogen *trans* to H_A and *geminal* to H_B. This is also a doublet of doublet with *J* values 18 and 5 Hz. The assignments are consistent with the fact that *J*_{geminal} is 18 Hz and that the *cis* and *trans* vicinal coupling constants in a five-membered ring with a double bond are around 12 and 5 Hz respectively².

In general, all the hydrogens appear a bit downfield in nitroso derivatives compared to the corresponding acetyl derivatives. In the parent pyrazolines, H_A appears at δ 4.02, H_B at 3.35 and H_C at 2.90 respectively³. Both the acetyl and nitroso derivatives have all their hydrogens deshielded compared to the parent as these groups are electron-withdrawing, the deshielding effect of nitroso group being more significant than the acetyl group. There is no significant change in the stereochemistry of these two systems (1 and 3) as the *J*_{cis} and *J*_{trans} values of these are comparable. It should be mentioned that the *trans*- and *cis*-coupling values vary between δ 3.9 to 10.5 and 11.5 to 13.5 respectively, for various other 2-pyrazolines⁴. For bicyclic 2-pyrazolines, the *trans*-coupling is as high as 13 Hz⁵. The *ortho*-hydrogens of the aryl group (R₁) at position-3 are deshielded by the anisotropic effect of the double bond. The acetyl or nitroso group at position-1 does not seem to exert any such effect on the aryl hydrogens (R₂) at posi-

TABLE 1—*N*-SUBSTITUTED-3,5-DIARYL-2-PYRAZOLINES*

Compd. no.	Yield** %	M.p. °C	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	
			C=O/N=O	C=N
1a	75	121	1585	1550
3a	83	125	1640	1585
1b	78	124	1580	1555
3b	70	Oil	1640	1580
1c	90	135	1580	1550
3c	90	108–09	1645	1580
1d	90	140–42	1585	1550
3d	–	Oil	1640	1585
1e	78	138	1580	1550
3e	88	104	1650	1575
1f	78	135	1580	1555
3f	85	100	1630	1580
1g	81	157	1580	1550
3g	85	128	1630	1575
1h	75	133	1585	1550
3h	90	108	1650	1570

*Elemental analyses are within $\pm 0.04\%$ error. **Yields are with respect to the parent pyrazoline.

TABLE 2-PMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF N-SUBSTITUTED-3,5-DIARYL-2-PYRAZOLINES*
(δ -scale, CDCl₃)

Compd. no.	ArH R ₁	ArH R ₂	H _A (dd)	H _B (dd)	H _C (dd)	others
1a	8.10 (2H, ortho) 7.65 (3H, others)	7.2-7.5 (Multiplet)	5.85 (12, 5 Hz)	3.90 (18, 12 Hz)	3.25 (18, 5 Hz)	-
3a	7.85 (2H, ortho) 7.55 (3H, others)	7.4 (Singlet)	5.65 (12, 6 Hz)	3.75 (18, 12 Hz)	3.15 (18, 6 Hz)	2.45 (s, COCH ₃)
1b	7.45, 8.0 (AA'BB')	7.2 (Singlet)	5.80 (12, 5 Hz)	3.80 (18, 10 Hz)	3.25 (18, 5 Hz)	2.30 (s, ArCH ₃)
3b	7.20, 7.70 (AA'BB')	7.15 (Singlet)	5.50 (12, 5 Hz)	3.65 (18, 12 Hz)	3.05 (18, 5 Hz)	2.40 (s, COCH ₃) 2.35 (s, ArCH ₃) 2.25 (s, ArCH ₃)
1c	7.60, 8.00 (AA'BB')	7.20, 7.45 (AA'BB')	5.80 (12, 5 Hz)	3.90 (18, 12 Hz)	3.20 (18, 5 Hz)	-
3c	7.70, 8.00 (AA'BB')	7.45, 7.60 (AA'BB')	5.80 (13, 5 Hz)	3.85 (18, 13 Hz)	3.20 (18, 5 Hz)	2.50 (s, COCH ₃)
1d	7.50, 8.05 (AA'BB')	7.00, 7.25 (AA'BB')	5.95 (12, 5 Hz)	3.95 (18, 12 Hz)	3.25 (18, 5 Hz)	3.85 (s, OCH ₃) 3.95 (s, OCH ₃)
3d	6.95, 7.80 (AA'BB')	7.05, 7.30 (AA'BB')	5.55 (12, 5 Hz)	3.85 (18, 12 Hz)	3.05 (18, 5 Hz)	3.75 (s, OCH ₃) 3.85 (s, OCH ₃)
1e	8.10 (2H, ortho) 7.65 (3H, others)	7.25 (Singlet)	5.85 (11, 5 Hz)	3.85 (18, 11 Hz)	3.25 (18, 5 Hz)	2.30 (s, ArCH ₃)
3e	7.60 (2H, ortho) 7.40 (3H, others)	7.20 (Singlet)	5.60 (11, 5 Hz)	3.75 (18, 11 Hz)	3.15 (18, 5 Hz)	2.30 (s, ArCH ₃) 2.40 (s, COCH ₃)
1f	Poor solubility in common nmr solvents					
3f	7.95 (2H, ortho) 7.65 (3H, others)	7.00, 7.40 (AA'BB')	5.70 (12, 5 Hz)	3.80 (18, 12 Hz)	3.20 (18, 5 Hz)	3.85 (s, OCH ₃) 2.45 (s, COCH ₃)
1g	Not completely soluble in common nmr solvents					
3g	7.25, 8.00 (AA'BB')	7.66 (Singlet)	5.80 (12, 5 Hz)	3.85 (18, 12 Hz)	3.25 (18, 5 Hz)	4.00 (s, OCH ₃) 2.50 (s, COCH ₃)
1h	7.40, 7.90 (AA'BB')	7.50 (Singlet)	5.75 (13 Hz, 5 Hz)	3.65 (18, 13 Hz)	3.10 (18, 5 Hz)	2.45 (s, ArCH ₃)
3h	7.40, 7.80 (AA'BB')	7.40 (Singlet)	5.70 (13 Hz, 5 Hz)	3.80 (18, 13 Hz)	3.15 (18, 5 Hz)	2.25 (s, ArCH ₃) 2.50 (s, COCH ₃)

*In CDCl₃.

tion-5. Interestingly, the methyl or methoxy group of the aryl at 3-position appears slightly upfield compared to their counterparts in the 5-position.

References

- (a) A. A. KHALAF, R. A. KABLI, M. T. ZIMAITY, A. M. KHALIL, A. M. KADDAH and H. A. AL-RAIFAIE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 1125; (b) A. A. KHALAF, R. A. KABLI, M. T. ZIMAITY, A. M. KHALIL, A. M. KADDAH and H. A. AL-RAIFAIE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 47, and the references cited therein.
- R. C. COOKSON, T. A. CRABB, J. J. FRANKEL and J. HUDBEE, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, **7**, 355.
- "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. KATRITZKY and C. W. REES, Pergamon, London, 1984, Vol. 5, p. 78.
- W. S. BREIS and C. M. VALENICA, *Can J Chem*, 1968, **46**, 810; D. B. REDDY, G. V. B. REDDY, A. PADMAJA and N. S. REDDY, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1995, **4**, 179.
- A. A. KHALAF, A. K. EL-SHAFFI and A. M. EL-SAYEED, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1982, **19**, 609.